

LISA

LASER IONISATION AND SPECTROSCOPY OF ACTINIDES

SHINING LIGHT ON THE HEAVIEST ELEMENTS

15 early stage researchers working with **25 institutions**, coming together in **one network**, the LISA Network.

We strive to understand the heaviest elements using laser-based techniques

We link industrial partners to research institutions

We want to share our knowledge through outreach and education

WE STUDY:

- Atomic structure
- Laser performance
- Nuclei of rare heavy elements

WE AIM TO:

- Understand challenging nuclear and atomic structure models
- Produce radio-isotopes for medicine
- Analyse radio-isotope traces in the environment

WE WORK TO DEVELOP:

- Radioactive ion beam facilities
- Wavelength-tuneable laser technology
- Experimental methods
- Theoretical modelling software

GET INVOLVED

- **Do you work in the same fields as LISA?**
Follow the network's scientific results!
- **Do you want to gain research experience with LISA?**
Follow our upcoming training events!
- **Are you interested in science?**
Look out for our upcoming outreach events!

More information: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

#LISA_ITN

Beneficiaries:

Partners:

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